
Pilot report

EASA

QUESTION 1

R&I RESOURCES AND STRATEGIC AGENDA

The key objective of this project is to produce a detailed report on the current potential and challenges of creating a research database, identifying and recording relevant sources for the production and exhibition of short animated films in small European countries. The aim is to understand the future funding and resources needed for the creation of an archived relational database containing information on European short animated film, as a resource for theoretical and artistic research. That such a resource does not exist in a readily accessible format is a bar to basic research in key areas of film practice and artistic research, as well as for studies in the history and significance of the medium. It is our aim that such an exercise will reveal the historical and current landscape of practice in animated short film production, thereby suggesting the types of research activity that become possible and pointing to directions in research and practice that are not now possible to conceive, as such an archive - comprehensive, accessible, searchable and consistent - does not exist.

IMPACT & ENGAGEMENT

This pilot has been presented to several constituencies within FilmEU, including the annual Summit, doctoral seminars, and research events. The pilot team met regularly, including an in-person three-day working meeting in Paris, where the information we'd gathered was framed into our final outputs.

It has been included in FilmEU_RIT publicity materials.

The code for the database has been shared in GitHub as an open-source resource for researchers.

Access to the database is available by request, which has been granted to a number of people who are conducting investigations into animation theory and practice.

Resources gathered are available to future researchers and pilots within the consortium should they wish to build on this work.

TALENT

Despite presenting this pilot in a number of Film EU_RIT fora, we were not joined by any

other members of the consortium, so were not able to develop in those areas beyond the four original members of the pilot team.

NETWORKING

The elements of networking in this pilot consist primarily of the work the core team of four have done together, as well as presentations we have made in various Film EU forums such as annual Summits and to doctoral researchers. However, it has also borne fruit in that the group members have collaborated in other institutional contexts, such as serving on interview panels and as external examiners in each other's programmes, cementing relationships and creating collaboration in the wider sector.

Case Study

We created a test database from the material gathered by each of the team members, as a proof of concept for the research potential that lies in assembling these scattered and partial resources into one place. We intended this proof-of-concept as a test case for understanding the commonalities and differences in resources for researchers and investigators in animation studies in small European countries. What kinds of questions would arise (that are currently difficult to ask) if there was a central repository of information? How would scholars in our three countries be facilitated to add to the corpus of animation scholarship? What kinds of research clusters might be fostered, and how might they intersect with other clusters in the consortium? How could the database become interactive, so that scholars might share new information or correct the record as their research progresses? Of the hundreds of potential titles for inclusion, we narrowed our lists to forty per country. We attempted to include a range of time frames, producers, subjects, media, and styles.

It is a non-scientific but useful array of material for testing and analysis. There are 120 short animated films in a searchable pre-alpha database. Access to the interface may be gained via contacting one of the team, as this is not yet ready for wide release, but we would like it to be available to interested researchers or to teams in FilmEU who would like to take this further.

An initial decision-making process was undertaken to determine categories for classification and searching that would be

straightforward, combinable, and foster common initial approaches to formulating research questions. The categories were also chosen as a way of rationalising what we found in the sources from which this information was drawn, which were quite variable with differing levels of depth. We chose to start with a modest range of useful categories:

Director: Director's Gender: Production House: Release Year: Duration: Country of Production: Languages.

In lieu of creating a robust metadata system, we chose in the first instance to use a system of tags to gather relevant information that could later be used to determine metadata categories. These categories are a minimum starting point, with wide potential for expansion and detail.

It became clear to us that categories could easily be added for all production functions, with information drawn from film credit sequences. This would immediately provide a list of roles and personnel for animated production in our countries, with potential for understanding similarities and differences, and tracing changes over time. Even for a modest number of films, this would provide a body of information for analysis that does not now exist.

QUESTION 2

Any challenge or barrier to reporting, in particular in these topics, core to the dynamic clusters:

The main challenges we faced each contain some element of the three categories in this area (interinstitutional collaboration, interdisciplinary collaboration, inter-human collaboration), so they are being treated as a body in this response.

No easy way to share widely: Having gathered a body of useful information and resources, it also became clear to us that there is currently no mechanism within the consortium for scholars to easily create and share collaborative work in digital formats across the partner institutions. There is no way of efficiently uploading and sharing our reference files and database beyond hosting it on one of the partner institution's proprietary platforms, or without creating an external arrangement that requires oversight across time. Simply put, there's currently nowhere to place our work in a common

resource bank so that it can be accessible to scholars, one of the key impulses informing our proposal. This means we were unable to test the pilot database fully by offering it freely to others in the consortium. Creating such a mechanism would foster the overall goals of FilmEU_RIT, particularly in research collaboration, and should be considered in future.

Transitory funding hinders partnerships: The institutions we contacted regarding collaboration with this project each expressed concern about the nature of European projects in general, noting that they tended to fade away when funding ends, leaving partnerships behind. Requesting the labour of their archivists and librarians has real implications for these institutions, which are frequently underfunded and under pressure from too much work and too few staff. Gathering the disparate resources they hold into a centralised database means any joint project must have persistence across time, and a mechanism that makes information and resources available in ways that create value for all involved. There is enormous potential for FilmEU to make an impact in this arena, but it will require committing people and funding to a long-term effort.

Lack of participation from the wider consortium: While we are still convinced of the validity of our initial statements regarding the role of short animated film within the corpus of cinema history and practice, we also note that to date there has been no additional interest in our project area from within the consortium partners. It was our expectation that we would be joined by postgraduate scholars or members of staff, but that has not materialised, despite having shared and presented this work in several fora. Should it proceed, this project holds the potential to become a large-scale undertaking requiring expertise not contained within the current group of four, who are all senior in their institutions with a range of other pressing responsibilities in their core positions. This may change in the future as the consortium expands, and in that case the work we've done is available to be taken up by other elements of the consortium, or included in other project areas. However, this returns us to the above point - the material needs to be held in a central Film EU repository, where it can become accessible to interested parties as the current members of this group move into new roles and responsibilities at the close of this pilot phase.

QUESTION 3

What management /collaboration tool did the Pilot Team use? How did the team use it, for what main purpose, and how did you evaluate it?

Because our team was small, we used Microsoft Teams to collaborate and share files and information. Our institutions and FilmEU had this ready-made tool available, and it was convenient and secure. We didn't need anything else, and there was no need for detailed evaluation as it worked seamlessly for the nature of the project and for the team.

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